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A VARIATION IN ENERGY EFFICIENT ROUTING METHOD RESULTING IN THE HIGH QUALITY ROUTING PERFORMANCE FOR L-PEDAP

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Abstract

Wireless Sensor Networks is a collection of wireless sensor nodes dynamically forming a temporary network without the aid of any established infrastructure or centralized administration. Routing protocols in wireless sensor networks helps node to send and receive packets. Traditional hierarchical routing algorithms combine adaptability to changing environments with energy aware aspects. In this random mobility model structure, which nodes can construct from the position of their 1-hop neighbors. This also describes route maintenance protocols to respond to predicted sensor failures and addition of new sensors. Localized – Power Efficient Data Aggregation Protocol (L-PEDAP) and Ad hoc on demand Distance Vector routing protocol (AODV) are compared. The performance of these two routing protocols (L-PEDAP, AODV) is based on metrics such as packet delivery ratio, end to end delay; energy consumption and throughput, also this work will analyze and compare the performance of protocols using NS-2.34, when various other mobility models are applied to these protocols.

Keywords - mobile sensor networks, mobile node, mobility model.

1. INTRODUCTION

WSN are self-configuring, self-healing networks consisting of mobile or static sensor nodes connected wirelessly to form an arbitrary topology. WSN are not currently deployed on a large scale, research in this area is mostly simulation based [1]. Mobile wireless sensor networks owe its name the presence of mobile sink. Advantage of mobile WSN over static WSN are better energy efficiency, improved coverage and enhance target tracking and superior channel capacity [2]. Mobility of the nodes affects the throughput of the protocol because the bandwidth reservation made or the control information exchanged may end with no use, if the node mobility is very high [3]. Figure 1 shows the mobile sensor network scenario in which the position of a mobile node at time t , $(t+1)$, and $(t+2)$ are shown as A, B and C respectively. Performance of routing protocols is studied with the MANETS using different mobility models. Among other simulation parameters, the mobility model plays a very important role in determining the protocol performance in MSN. Hence it is essential to study and analyze various mobility models and their effect on MSN. This paper compares the

two different protocols with two mobility models and their performance with parameters like Packet delivery ratio, End to End delay, Energy consumption and throughput in MSN. Figure 2 shows the design flow of how the mobility metrics are added to the mobility model and the protocol performance with the connected paths is analyzed.

Figure 1. MOBILE SENSOR NETWORK SCENARIO

II. RELATED WORKS

The effects of various mobility models and the performance of two routing protocols Dynamic Source Routing (DSR-Reactive Protocol) and Destination Sequenced Distance Vector (DSDV-Proactive Protocol) is studied in [4]. Performance comparison has also been conducted across varying node densities and number of hops. Experiment results illustrate that performance of the routing protocol varies across different mobility models, node densities and length of data paths. Mobile wireless ad hoc networks are infrastructure less and often used to operate under unattended mode. So, it is significant in bringing out a comparison of the various routing protocols for better understanding and implementation of them. In this paper, comparison of the performance of various routing protocols like Ad hoc On-Demand Vector routing (AODV), Localized-Power Efficient Data Aggregation Protocol are discussed. The comparison results were graphically depicted and explained [5].

Figure 2. Design Flow

The mobility model is the most important factors in the performance evaluation of a mobile ad hoc network (MANET). Traditionally, the random waypoint mobility model has been used to model the node mobility, where the movement of one node is modeled as independent from all others. However, in large scale military scenarios, mobility coherence among nodes is quite common. One typical mobility behavior is group mobility. Thus, to investigate military MANET scenarios, an underlying realistic mobility model is highly desired. In this paper a “virtual track” based group mobility model (VT model) which closely approximates the mobility patterns in military MANET scenarios is proposed. It models various types of node mobility such as group moving nodes, individually moving nodes as well as static nodes. Moreover, the VT model not only models the group mobility, it also models the dynamics of group mobility such as group merge and split. Simulation experiments show that the choice of mobility model has significant impact on network performance [6]

III. MOBILITY MODELS

Mobility models consist of two different types of Dependencies such as spatial and temporal dependency. Mobility of a node may be constrained and limited

by the physical laws of acceleration, velocity and rate of change of direction. Spatial dependence is a measure of node mobility direction. Two nodes moving in same direction have high spatial dependency. The current velocity of a mobile node may depend on its previous velocity. The velocities of single node at different time slots are correlated. This mobility characteristic is called as the temporal dependency of velocity [1]. Frequently used mobility models includes Random waypoint, Manhattan, Energy consumption model. We compare the performance of these models with parameters like packet delivery ratio, end to end delay, energy consumption and throughput, and hop count using two different routing protocols.

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A. **Random way point mobility model**

The Random Waypoint model is the most commonly used mobility model in research community. At every instant, a node randomly chooses a destination and moves towards it with a velocity chosen randomly from a uniform distribution $[0, V_{max}]$, where V_{max} is the maximum allowable velocity for every mobile node. After reaching the destination, the node stops for a duration defined by the 'pause time' parameter. After this duration, it again chooses a random destination and repeats the whole process until the simulation ends. Figures 3 illustrate examples of a topography showing the movement of nodes for Random Mobility Model.

Figure 3. Topography Showing The Movement Of Nodes For Random Mobility Model.

B. **Energy Consumption Model**

There are different models proposed for modeling energy consumption in sensor nodes. Here, we use the first order radio model proposed in [2]. In this model, the energy consumed to transmit a k bit packet to a distance d (denoted as E_{tx}) and the energy consumed to receive a k bit packet (denoted as E_{rx}) are given as follows:

$$E_{tx}(k,d) = ak + bkd^n, E_{rx}(k) = ck. \quad (1)$$

In this model, a and c are the energy consumption constants of the transmit and receiver electronics, respectively, and b is the energy consumption constant for the transmit amplifier. There are various studies in the literature based on this model. S.Singh et al. [2] propose and use this model, assuming that $a=c=50, b=0.1$ and $n=2$. On the other hand, in [10], $(a+c) = 2 \times 10^8, b=1,$ and $n=4$.

According to proposed model, the total energy cost of transmitting a k bit packet from a node i to a neighboring node j as $C_{ij}(k)$, then $C_{ij}(k)$ is given as follows.

$$C_{ij}(k) = ak + bkd^{m_{ij}}, \text{ if } j \text{ is sink.} \quad (2)$$

The costs of transmission of one packet to another node and to the sink are different, since the sink has no energy constraints and its cost for receiving messages is ignored.

IV. ROUTING PROTOCOLS

A. Ad-Hoc on Demand Distance Vector Routing (AODV)

AODV is a distance vector type routing protocol. This protocol does not maintain the routes to destination that are not activity used .Till the nodes have valid routes to each other AODV does not play a role. It uses Router request (RREQ) .Route replies (RREPs). Route error (RERR). message to discover and maintain the routes. When a node wants a route to a destination it broadcasts RREQ to the entire network till the destination is reached or a fresh route is found. Then a RREP is send back to the source with the discovered path. When the node detects the route is not valid it broadcasts a RERR message [4] [7].

B. Localized – Power Efficient Data Aggregation Routing Protocol(L-PEDAP)

L-PEDAP is table driven algorithm based on Lmst routing .Each node has a routing table having the destination, next hop and number of hops to the destination. The nodes periodically broadcast the updates. A sequence number is tagged with time also the shortest path to a destination is used .if a node detects route to a destination is broken then the hop number is set to infinity and its sequence number is updated to a odd number .Even numbers represent the sequence numbers of connected paths. The sequence numbers enable the mobile nodes to distinguish stale routes from new ones, thereby avoiding the formation of routing loops [4] [7] [8]

V. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

Each model is implemented with the L-PEDAP and AODV protocols and their performance is analyzed with various node densities such as 10,20,30,40 and 50 with standard 802.11 MAC layer. The packet type generated in the trace file is UDP .In the simulation scenario we used omni directional antennas with transmission range 250m.Our simulation

results has shown that packet delivery ratio is higher in L-PEDAP when compared with AODV. Energy consumption and End to End delay is less in L-PEDAP when compared with AODV.

TABLE 1 SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Area	1000m X 1000m
MAC	IEEE 802.15.4
Transmission Range	250m
No of Source Nodes	10,20,30,40,50
Simulation Time(sec)	180sec
Mobility	Random Waypoint
Traffic Type	CBR
Transport Layer	UDP
Packet Size	1400 bytes

A. PACKET DELIVERY FRACTION

In the figure X axis represents the varying number of node and y axis represents the packet delivery fraction

Figure 4: PACKET DELIVERY FRACTION

based on the Figure 4, it is shown than L-PEDAP perform better when the number of nodes increases because nodes become more stationary will lead to more stable path from source to destination AODV performance dropped as number of nodes increase because more packets dropped due to link breaks.

B. END – TO - END DELAY

In the figure X axis represents the varying number of nodes and y axis represents the end to end delay in mille seconds.

Figure 5.END TO END DELAY

Based on Figure 5, L-PEDAP didn't produce so much delay even the number of nodes increased. It is better than AODV protocols.

C. ENERGY CONSUMPTION

In the figure X axis represents the varying number of nodes and y axis represents the end to end delay in mille seconds.

Figure 6: ENERGY CONSUMPTION

From Figure 6 L-PEDAP less prone to route stability compared to AODV. For L-PEDAP, the routing consumption is not so affected as generated in AODV.

D.THROUGHPUT

In the figure X axis represents the varying number of node and y axis represents the throughput.

Figure 7. THROUGHPUT

The number of packets received in L-PEDAP is higher when compared to AODV protocol. It is also dependent of time. When time increase number of packet received at receiver side also increases correspondingly.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The performance of L-PEDAP and AODV routing protocol were measured with respect to metrics like Packet Delivery Ratio, End to End Delay, Energy consumption, throughput by single scenarios, (number of node). The results indicate that the performance of L-PEDAP is superior to regular AODV. It is also observed that the performance is better, especially when the number of nodes in the network is higher. When the number of nodes increased beyond 20 and above, the performance of proactive AODV degenerated due to the facts that a lot of control packets are generated. It is also observed that L-PEDAP is better than AODV protocol in both PDR and Throughput. The reason for the performance to get drop at 10 to 20 nodes is due to varying source and destination

nodes and placement barrier in network topology. It is concluded that the performance of AODV is high in Energy Consumption and End to End delay when the no of node is high (link breakage occurred) when compared to L-PEDAP. Furthermore, performance comparison can be done with other mobility models .In future X-LLC protocol will be implemented for scenario and it will be compared with the exiting protocol (AODV and L-PEDAP).

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